

D7.1 Project logo, marketing starter pack and website running

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Project coordinator: Prof Dr Benjamin Burkhard, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz University Hannover

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1 Preface

One of the main objectives of WP7 “Dissemination and knowledge sharing” is to create and maintain a recognisable project identity. WP7 also aims to provide an optimal level of popularisation of project results by promoting and disseminating them across stakeholders and the general public. To ensure the continuous and consistent impact of SELINA outputs, WP7 has developed the foundation of the visual identity for all project-related materials, as well as the main channel for dissemination of results – the project website. All material was available for use and distribution at the SELINA Kick-off-Meeting in September 2022.

2 Summary

The following report presents the initial project branding and marketing products that showcase the project’s visual identity and overall corporate appearance.

As a foundation of effective future communication activities, a sound set of working dissemination tools and materials is crucial to be established within the first months of the project. A project logo, project promotional materials, overall visual identity package, and a public website (www.project-selina.eu) were developed in the first 3 months of the project duration in order to form the main tools of project public visibility and internal communication.

The project is provided with a logo that has been communicated and coordinated with all project partners. Dissemination materials such as the SELINA brochure and poster were produced for raising awareness and engaging stakeholders at events. A project visual identity/brand manual was created and circulated among project partners in order to provide a consistent visual representation of the project. A set of corporate templates was also produced and made available to the Consortium partners to facilitate future dissemination and reporting activities such as milestones and deliverable reports, PowerPoint presentations, posters etc. The project website is developed as the main dissemination channel.

The longer-term impact of the project's results will be secured by maintaining the website for a minimum of 5 years after the end of the project.

3 Project logo

The project logo was designed to help the external audience to easily identify the SELINA project and it contributes to the project's visibility by providing a corporate identity from the very beginning. The logo is based on the logo of SELINA's predecessor project, ESMERALDA, reflecting the continuity and lasting impact of that project's results, as they form the basis upon which SELINA stands. The nature-based colours and map-shaped design are also a reference to the core element of the project, ecosystem mapping, while the dotted design reflects the international, collaborative effort upon which the success of the project relies. The logo is publicly available and can be downloaded by the consortium and external stakeholders, including the media, from the SELINA website (<https://project-selina.eu/media-center/logo>).

For the purpose of better visual representation and a higher suitability of the logo for all marketing purposes of SELINA, the project logo was developed in two main versions – a short version (Fig. 1 – Fig.3), and a full version that includes the full name of the project (Figures 4 - 6). Both versions are available in colour, all-black, and all-white, and in three formats (.jpg, .png, and .svg vector).

Figure 1: SELINA logo (short, colour).

Figure 2: SELINA logo (short, black).

Figure 3: SELINA logo (short, white).

Figure 4: SELINA logo (full version, colour).

Figure 5: SELINA logo (full version, black).

Figure 6: SELINA logo (full version, white).

4 Initial marketing materials pack

4.1. The SELINA QR codes

The SELINA QR codes were designed to direct target groups to the SELINA website and social media channels (Fig. 7). Used on most marketing materials, the QR codes will be a key element of promotional efforts to raise awareness and build a community around the project.

Figure 7: The SELINA QR codes (for website and social media).

4.2. The SELINA brochure

The SELINA brochure was designed to capture the attention of the different target groups and increase awareness of the project. It explains the consortium's vision for the project and the project's mission, including specific objectives and how they are going to be achieved; it also highlights the project's most important elements and characteristics (Fig. 8). The brochure

was created to reflect the conceptual design of the project logo and website and was subject to discussions and improvements from across the project consortium.

OUR VISION

SELINA will provide guidance for **evidence-based decision-making** that supports the protection, restoration, and sustainable use of our environment.

Through a collaboration of experts from 50 partner organisations from all 27 EU member states, Norway, Switzerland, Israel, and the United Kingdom, SELINA will set **new standards for international cooperation** to promote Ecosystem Services (ES) and Biodiversity (BD) conservation and enhance Ecosystem Conditions (EC).

Providing robust practical information and recommendations to stakeholders from both the public and private sectors, SELINA will pave the way towards the **transformative societal change** required to achieve the ambitious goals of the European Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and the Green Deal.

OUR MISSION

What: Identify BD, EC, and ES factors that can be successfully integrated into public and private sectors' decision-making processes

How: Facilitate and harness knowledge-sharing and co-production via EU-wide workshops and multi-disciplinary Communities of Practice

What: Develop, test, and integrate new and existing knowledge, including methodological approaches to improve BD, EC, and ES information uptake by decision-makers

How: Build a fit-for-purpose knowledge base about mapping and assessing terrestrial and aquatic EC, their ES, and links between them that apply to various decision-making contexts

What: Demonstrate how enhanced collaboration between science, private, and public stakeholders facilitates BD, EC, and ES integration in evidence-based decision-making

How: Organise Demonstration Projects on BD, EC, and ES integration in decision-making and co-create a Compendium of Guidance with representatives from science, society, and the public and private sectors

WHAT MAKES SELINA UNIQUE

A **multinational interdisciplinary network of professionals** ranging from ecologists, economists, and social scientists to decision-makers of all levels

A compilation of the **most complete and up-to-date knowledge base on ES**, integrating new and existing knowledge built through various EU projects and global initiatives

Practical, **fit-for-purpose recommendations** with real-world applications in policy making and business decisions

An unprecedented opportunity for smart, cost-effective and **nature-based solutions** to historic societal challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and food security

Figure 8: SELINA brochure.

4.3. The SELINA poster

The SELINA poster was produced at the beginning of the project with an eye-catching design, illustrating the project's vision and most important elements and characteristics. The poster reflects the main SELINA design concept to keep the project branding consistent and to make the project easily recognizable (Fig. 9). This poster will be used to introduce the project at conferences, meetings and stakeholder events.

Figure 9: The SELINA poster.

4.4. The SELINA banner

The SELINA banner (Fig. 10) was produced to be used in conferences, meetings, and stakeholder events, in order to enrich the project's visual presence. In line with the project's overall visual identity, it showcases the SELINA logo and full title and invites the audience to follow the SELINA project on social media via a QR code.

Figure 10: The SELINA banner.

4.5. The SELINA 4-pager

The SELINA 4-pager (Fig. 11) was produced as a quick introduction to the project; a means of easily educating target audiences about the project's Partners, main aims, expected outcomes, and work packages. This 4-pager will be used in conferences, meetings, and stakeholder events.

The SELINA 4-pager is a four-page document designed to provide a quick introduction to the project. It is structured as follows:

- Page 1 (Top Left):** Project Summary. Features a world map graphic and the title "SELINA AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT ABOUT NATURAL CAPITAL". It outlines the project's goal to provide guidance for evidence-based decision-making, lists partner organizations from 27 EU member states, and identifies the project coordinator, Prof. Dr. Benjamin Burkhard.
- Page 2 (Top Right):** Description of Work Packages. A flowchart showing the integration of 11 work packages (WP 1-11) into a cohesive project structure. WP 1 is Coordination & Project Integration. WP 2-5 focus on stakeholder networking and decision-making processes. WP 6-8 focus on ecosystem services mapping and assessment. WP 9-10 focus on evidence-based public and private decision-making. WP 11 is the Science Policy Society Platform for guidance development.
- Page 3 (Bottom Left):** Ecosystem services mapping and assessment, Ecosystem accounting, and Integrated assessment. This page details the methodologies for mapping ecosystem services, accounting for them in decision-making, and integrating this information with other data.
- Page 4 (Bottom Right):** Expected Outcomes, Project Partners, and Office Requirements. It lists the project's goals, such as producing evidence-based guidance and supporting decision-making. It also lists 27 project partners from various European countries and provides information on office requirements.

Figure 11 (4 images): The SELINA 4-pager.

4.6. The SELINA visual identity guide

The SELINA visual identity guide is a document that contains all essential guidelines to the SELINA visual identity. It serves as a brand manual; a reference point for all project partners, aiming to guarantee a consistent and continuous presentation of project outputs, such as presentations, project documents, promotional materials and others. The SELINA visual identity guide includes two versions of the SELINA brand identity (light and dark version), the project's colour codes and fonts, as well as some visual materials that aim to promote and strengthen the visual identity and corporate image of the project.

The visual identity of the project was communicated to all project partners during the Kick-off Meeting and is also available to download via the SELINA Internal Repository, which is accessible by all project partners via the project's website (via login).

The SELINA brand manual is enclosed in **Annex 1** of this Deliverable.

4.7. The SELINA corporate identity templates

SELINA corporate identity templates were designed in the very beginning of the project to make sure all project partners use a consistent visual presentation on project-related topics.

The templates include:

- Deliverable report
- Milestone report
- PowerPoint presentation
- Poster

Each template is specifically tailored to the information the respective document is required to contain. The templates incorporate the SELINA project logo and suggest the information necessary to be included in the document.

All templates are made available and easy to access for all partners via the Internal Repository.

4.8. The SELINA website

The official website of the SELINA project (www.project-selina.eu) (Fig. 12) was designed to act as an information hub about the project's aims, goals, activities and results. The website serves as a prime public dissemination tool making the project's output, including public deliverables and published materials available to all stakeholders and the general public. The events organized by SELINA or of relevance to the project are also announced through the website, as well as all major developments of the project. Published open access scientific output will also be included in the project's public library on the project website.

SELINA

SCIENCE FOR EVIDENCE-BASED AND SUSTAINABLE DECISIONS ABOUT NATURAL CAPITAL

Vision

To pave the way towards the **transformative societal change** required to achieve the ambitious goals of the European Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and the Green Deal.

Mission

To enhance **decision-making** processes within the public and private sectors by improving the quality of Biodiversity, Ecosystem Conditions, and Ecosystem Services information.

Goal

To harness the power of **transdisciplinary knowledge sharing** and provide guidance for the protection, restoration, and sustainable use of our environment.

SELINA in numbers

50

Partners

31

Countries

5

Years duration

Latest News

17 November 2022

New EU Project Selina Launched: Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services Experts From 31 Countries Met in Hannover

1 July 2022

EU Project at the Forefront of International Environmental Protection and Restoration Efforts

Latest Events

4 - 7 October 2022
The Entrepreneurial Building, Brussels BE

EU Bioeconomy Conference 2022

11 - 14 October 2022
Ginkgo Hotel Frankfurt, Central DE

4th ESP Europe Conference

16 - 19 October 2022
The City, Brussels BE

European Business and Nature Summit 2022

Latest updates

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ABOUT THE PROJECT

Our Vision

SELINA will provide guidance for evidence-based decision-making that supports the protection, restoration, and sustainable use of our environment. Through a collaboration of experts from 50 partner organisations from all 27 EU member states, Norway, Switzerland, Israel, and the United Kingdom, SELINA will set new standards for international cooperation to promote Ecosystem Services (ES) and Biodiversity (BD) conservation and enhance Ecosystem Conditions (EC).

Providing robust practical information and recommendations to stakeholders from both the public and private sectors, SELINA will pave the way towards the transformative societal change required to achieve the ambitious goals of the European Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and the Green Deal.

Our Mission

- What:** Identify BD, EC, and ES factors that can be successfully integrated into public and private sectors' decision-making processes
How: Facilitate and harness knowledge-sharing and co-production via EU-wide workshops and multi-disciplinary Communities of Practice
- What:** Develop, test, and integrate new and existing knowledge, including methodological approaches to improve BD, EC, and ES information uptake by decision-makers
How: Build a fit-for-purpose knowledge base about mapping and assessing terrestrial and aquatic EC, their ES, and links between them that apply to various decision-making contexts
- What:** Demonstrate how enhanced collaboration between science, private, and public stakeholders facilitates BD, EC, and ES integration in evidence-based decision-making
How: Organise Demonstration Projects on BD, EC, and ES integration in decision-making and co-create a Compendium of Guidance with representatives from science, society, and the public and private sectors

What makes SELINA unique

- A multinational transdisciplinary network of professionals ranging from ecologists, economists, and social scientists to decision-makers of all levels.
- A compilation of the most complete and up-to-date knowledge base on ES, integrating new and existing knowledge built through various EU projects and global initiatives
- Practical, fit-for-purpose recommendations with real-world applications in policy making and business decisions
- An unprecedented opportunity for smart, cost-effective and nature-based solutions to historic societal challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and food security

WP1	Coordination & project integration	+	WP2	Stakeholder networking & decision-making processes	+	WP3	Ecosystem type, biodiversity & condition mapping and assessment	+
WP4	Ecosystem services mapping and assessment	+	WP4	Ecosystem accounting	+	WP6	Integrated assessment	+
WP7	Dissemination and knowledge sharing	+	WP8	Supporting evidence-based public decision-making	+	WP9	Supporting evidence-based private decision-making	+
WP10	Science-Policy-Society Platform for guidance development	+	WP11	Ethics requirements	+			

ABOUT

The project
Structure
Partners

LATEST

News
Events
Library

RESOURCES

Media center

FOLLOW SELINA

CONTACT US

STAY UP TO DATE

Figure 12 (3 images): The SELINA website.

The website comprises of separate information pages with project background information, news, events, publications, contact details, etc. It is regularly updated to keep the audience

informed and ensure continued interest of already attracted visitors. The main website pages are:

- Homepage: contains introductory information about SELINA as well as latest events, news, and social media highlights related to the project
- About: introduces the vision and objectives of the project, as well as a description of SELINA's work packages
- Partners: presents the different project partners in a visually engaging way, including an interactive map view and a list view
- Library: a public subpage where all SELINA deliverables as well as all scientific publications resulting from the project will be made available
- News: a separate page where all SELINA outputs are presented in an engaging and informative manner
- Events: a public project calendar dedicated to all SELINA-organised and SELINA-relevant events
- Media Center: a place where all outreach materials (e.g. logo, brochure, poster etc.) are made available and can be downloaded freely and as necessary
- Contact: this page contains the contact information of the project coordinator
- Internal repository and communication platform

The project internal repository and communication platform is available only to project partners upon login (Fig.13). Once the user has logged into their profile, they are provided access to the SELINA mailing module, list of other registered users and storage area. The SELINA internal repository features project administrative documents, Deliverables and Milestones, document templates, meeting documents, and reporting forms (Fig. 14).

Figure 13: The SELINA internal repository login page.

Figure 14: The SELINA internal repository.

5 Conclusions

The SELINA branding and promotional materials are an integral part of the communication strategy and action of the project. The corporate visual identity of SELINA was integrated in the project's website and promotional materials to create an engaging environment for facilitation of the main communication and dissemination outputs of the project. Created at the beginning of the project, all elements of the visual identity of SELINA will be used during and beyond the project lifetime.

<https://project-selina.eu/>

6 Annex

- 3 Logo
- 6 Colour palette
- 7 Fonts
- 8 Visuals
- 12 Promotional materials

Logo 3

Full and short version

Logo 4

Full and short version – Dark background

SELINA – ALLER DISPLAY

**Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss
Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz**

SCIENCE FOR EVIDENCE-BASED AND SUSTAINABLE DECISIONS ABOUT NATURAL CAPITAL – ALLER DISPLAY

**Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss
Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz**

Logo

Heading 1 – Aller Display Bold

**Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo
Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz**

Heading 2 – Roboto bold

**Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww
Xx Yy Zz**

Body – Roboto

Bold: Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

Light: Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

Light Italic: Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

Headings and body text

Main image

Partners map

Visuals 11

Illustrations and icons

Promotional materials 12

Brochure

Poster

Sticker